

Notes

Spectral and Magnetic Properties of Copper(II) Complexes with 2-Aminopyrimidine and 2-Amino-4-methylpyrimidine

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PYRIMIDINE derivatives play a vital role in physiological system^{1,2} and complexes of its amino derivatives, viz. 2-aminopyrimidine (AP) and 2-amino-4-methylpyrimidine (AMP) with copper(II) is reported in the present communication.

Experimental

The ligands AP and AMP were obtained from Fluka.

Preparation of complexes: $CuCl_2$, $CuL_2 \cdot Br_2$, $CuL_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($L=AP$ or AMP) and $Cu(AP)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$: The complexes were obtained on refluxing methanolic (aqueous methanolic in case of sulphate) solution of copper(II) salts (0.01 ml in 50 ml) with hot methanolic solution of the ligand in 1:2 molar ratio. The nitrate and sulphate complexes were separated on concentrating and cooling the refluxate to small volume.

$Cu(AP)(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$: An aqueous ethanolic suspension of $Cu(AP)Cl_2$ was refluxed gently with 1:2 molar ratio of $NaNO_3$ on a steam-bath for

1 h. The complex was separated on concentrating and cooling the refluxate to a small volume. The products were filtered, washed with methanol and dried over $CaCl_2$.

The elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility value and electronic reflectance band positions of complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The hydrated complexes become anhydrous below 120° indicating that H_2O is not coordinated. The complexes have poor solubility in ethanol and methanol but dissolve appreciably in DMF. The DMF solution of the complexes shows small electrical conductance value suggesting the coordination of anions in these complexes. Except $CuCl_2$, the magnetic moment value of the other complexes are similar to magnetically dilute copper(II) complexes³⁻⁵. The solid reflectance spectra of complexes display a strong absorption above 21 500 cm^{-1} attributable to charge transfer band and a broad and asymmetric band at 10 650–17 500 cm^{-1} assignable to d-d transition (${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$) in distorted octahedral field⁶⁻¹⁰. The d-d transition of bis-ligated nitrate and sulphate complexes occur in the high energy region and are more symmetrical than dihalo complexes (Table 1) indicating less distortion in octahedral field^{9,10}. The ir spectra of ligands displays N-H stretching bands at 3 335 and 3 170 cm^{-1} in case of AP and at 3 302 and 3 160 cm^{-1} in AMP. The latter band shifts to lower frequency by 20–70 cm^{-1} in complexes indicating the coordination of amino nitrogen to metal atom^{11,12}. The $\beta(NH)$ of ligands (AP – 1 482 and AMP – 1 470 cm^{-1}) also shifts to higher frequencies attributable to coordination of amino nitrogen^{12,13}. The ν_{C-N} stretch located at 1 580

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		μ^* B.M.
		M	N	
$Cu(AP)Cl_2$	Bright green	27.45 (27.68)	18.21 (18.30)	1.72
$Cu(AP)_2Br_2$	Light brown	15.13 (15.37)	20.21 (20.32)	1.88
$Cu(AP)_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Violet blue	15.25 (15.36)	27.00 (27.06)	2.01
$Cu(AP)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	Violet blue	16.35 (16.47)	21.65 (21.78)	1.93
$Cu(AP)(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Greenish yellow	22.05 (22.16)	24.31 (24.42)	1.83
$Cu(AMP)Cl_2$	Bright green	26.02 (26.20)	17.02 (17.32)	1.73
$Cu(AMP)_2Br_2$	Light brown	14.31 (14.39)	19.00 (19.03)	1.86
$Cu(AMP)_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Violet blue	13.95 (14.38)	25.24 (25.36)	1.98
$Cu(AMP)(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Bright yellow	21.08 (21.13)	23.13 (23.34)	1.81

*Temp. = 00°C.

(AP) and 1590 cm^{-1} (AMP) splits into two bands and shifts to higher wave number by $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating that one of pyrimidine nitrogen is associated in bonding to copper(II) atom¹³.

The ir spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})(\text{ONO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1368 , $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1165 and 1140 and $\delta(\text{ONO})$ at 820 cm^{-1} . The unusual lowering of $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ in complex suggests oxygen bonding of NO_2 group in $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})(\text{ONO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The ir spectra of nitrate complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays ν_{NO_3} stretch at 1478 , 1278 and 1015 cm^{-1} which are characteristic frequencies of unidentate nitrate group¹⁴. The ir spectra of sulphato complex $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exhibits ν_{SO} at 1130 and 1030 (ν_{s} split) and 970 cm^{-1} (ν_1). The splitting of ν_{s} band indicates monocoordination of SO_4^{2-} group in $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex¹⁵. All the hydrated complexes display a broad and strong absorption near 3450 cm^{-1} due to water molecule. The $\rho_{\text{OH}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ could not be located near $680\text{--}85\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating absence of coordination of H_2O in the hydrated complexes¹⁴. Thus, from ir spectral studies, it is inferred that anions are coordinated and amino as well as one of pyrimidine ring nitrogen of the ligand are involved in bonding, probably as bridging group in complexes.

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Palladium(II) Complexes of some α -Oximinobenzoyl-acetarylamide Semicarbazones and Thiosemicarbazones

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THE present paper deals with the preparation and characterisation of palladium(II) complexes with the following α -oximinobenzoylacetarylamide semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones:

where, X=O (semicarbazone); X=S (thiosemicarbazone); R=H (α -oximinobenzoylacetylanilide), *o*-CH₃ or *p*-CH₃ (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-*o/p*-toluidide), *o*-Cl or *p*-Cl (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-*o/p*-chloroanilide), *o*-OCH₃ (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-*o*-aniside), and 2,4-(CH₃)₂ (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-2,4-xylidide).

Experimental

Aqueous solution of Pd⁺⁺ chloride (Johnson Matthey) (0.05 M; 10 ml) was gradually added to ethanolic solution (2%; 25 ml) of α -oximinobenzoylacetylanilide semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone and acidified with dilute HCl. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and digested on a steam-bath for 0.5 h. The precipitates separated were filtered, washed with hot water and aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) and dried in an oven at 110°. The Pd⁺⁺ chelates of the other α -oximinobenzoylacetarylamide semicarbazones/thiosemicarbazones of the series were prepared in the same manner. The complexes were bright yellow to golden yellow in colour and decomposed at $\approx 290^\circ$. Analytical data are given in Table 1.

Infrared spectra (KBr) of the ligands and complexes were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss UR-10 spectrophotometer fitted with LiF, NaCl and KBr prisms. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the finely powdered chelates were measured on a Beckman DU-10 spectrometer fitted with reflectance attachment, magnesium oxide being used as a reference material.

Results and Discussion

In ir spectra, of the ligands, the ν_{OH} band appears around $2800\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the